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A STRATEGY TYPOLOGY FOR DECISIONS ON BRAND STYLES AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION ON STYLING IN THE GERMAN AUTOMOTIVE MARKET

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ABSTRACT

Designers play a strategic role for companies in styling their branded products. However, while there are ample strategies for styling and branding, there are few typologies delineating the main strategic paths that companies can follow in styling new products, and even fewer typologies which link styling strategies to the branding strategies of companies. In this paper, we present a strategy typology for decisions on brand styles. Based on a cluster analysis of 173 car models, we distinguish four clusters of styling decisions, and discuss how these clusters relate to the branding strategies of automotive brands.

Keywords: styling, strategy, branding.

INTRODUCTION

Designers hold a pivotal role in styling new products in accordance with a brand's design philosophy (Karjalainen, 2004). Designers often nurture a recognizable style across the products belonging to a brand that is different from the competition. This is done to facilitate brand recognition and to transfer beliefs that consumers have for one product to other products falling under the same brand name. Styling is also used to introduce change in the appearance of products, making them more interesting and relevant to consumers in accordance with the current trends in the market (Moulson & Sproles, 2000). Moreover, the success of the Apple iMac and the diversity of styles in the mobile phones of Nokia suggest that a deviation from prior styles or the simultaneous use of different styles constitute common practice for styling.

The Swedish designer and design theorist Rune Monö (1997) proposed that many decisions of designers are about the relationship of a new product to existing

products. He identified three dimensions on which such relationships exist: (1) between a new product and the current product portfolio a company, (2) between a new product and the succession of previous product generations and (3) between a new product and competing products. Applying this model to the management of design, Warell (2001) suggested that the three dimensions describe a product's position on the market. Other research also suggests that, in styling new products, managers and designers seek different value contributions on these dimensions (Person, Snelders, Karjalainen, & Schoormans, 2007), and display stable decision patterns (i.e. 'styling strategies') in how they position the expression of new designs on them (Person, Schoormans, Snelders, & Karjalainen, 2008). However, no study addresses how decisions on one dimension potentially influence decisions on the other dimensions. In other words, no study has set out to describe what constitutes relevant combinations of decisions over Monö's three dimensions in styling new products.

In this paper, we present a strategy typology for decisions on brand styles. Specifically, we identify different combinations of styling decisions over Monö's three dimensions, and discuss how they relate to the branding strategies of automotive brands.

Since the early years of General Motors styling holds an undisputable role in the automotive industry (see e.g. Gartman, 2006). Major car manufacturers spend hundreds of millions of dollars in planning and conducting research on styling (Moulson & Sproles, 2000). Over the years, several methods have also been introduced to support automotive designers to take styling decisions (see e.g. McCormack, Cagan, & Vogel, 2004; Warell, 2001). However, few methods explicate the main strategic paths that automotive companies can follow in styling new products, and

even fewer have linked these to the branding strategies of such companies. Yet, studying these topics would provide designers and managers with valuable insights in pursuing styling activities more strategically.

METHOD

We based our typology on the different styling strategies found in the German passenger car market. Our focus on Germany follows the lead of an earlier study on styling in the automotive industry (Talke, Salomo, Wieringa, & Lutz, 2009). Germany constitutes the largest, and perhaps most competitive, car market in Europe. Most major car brands are present in the market. As a result, it provides a diverse stylistic scenery, grounded in the actions of multiple brands.

SAMPLE

We began by compiling a list of the main automotive brands operating in the German passenger car market by reviewing *Ward's World Motor Vehicle Data 2009* and new car registration data from the *European Automobile Manufacturers' Association* (ACEA). In doing so, we compiled a list of 39 automotive brands (see Table 1).

MEASURES

In developing our typology, we focused on the realized (implemented) strategies of automotive companies. Retrospective accounts of strategy by managers often differ significantly from the intended strategies reported by the same managers prior to implementation (Golden, 1992). Moreover, managers are often constrained in talking about what strategies they have pursued (Quinn, 1977). Accounting for these problems, we relied on the expertise of automotive design students for assessing

the brands' styling strategies and on industry experts for assessing the branding strategies underlying the different brands.

Domain experts have extensive up-to-date knowledge and pride themselves in staying informed about developments in their field of expertise (Shanteau, 1988). With a comparative view on the market, external experts are well suited for identifying the realized strategies of companies (Smith & Grimm, 1987). Hence, our automotive design students and industry experts provided in-depth knowledge on automotive styling and the automotive industry in general. This allowed us to acquire an independent and high-quality assessment of the brands' styling strategies and of the brands' general business strategies.

Styling strategy assessment

Styling strategies were assessed separately for each model by 15 Automotive designs students. The students were recruited from a Master program in Automotive design and were paid 20 Euros for their participation. Prior to the assessment, a representative set of models was selected for each brand. For this, we adopted the following procedure: To generate a list of available models, we visited the German websites of all the brands. To avoid an overestimation of coherence within a brand, we excluded versions that were presented as separate models, but that in reality had only limited (or no) difference to other versions in terms of their exterior styling (such as the Mini Cooper next to the Mini One). For the same reason, we also included one version of models that were sold as hatchback, sedan (saloon) or station wagon (estate) versions of the same model - and we always selected the hatchback over the sedan (for small cars), and the sedan over the station wagon (for larger cars).

<i>Alfa Romeo</i>	<i>Ford</i>	<i>Mazda</i>	<i>Seat</i>
<i>Audi</i>	<i>Honda</i>	<i>Mercedes-Benz</i>	<i>Skoda</i>
<i>BMW</i>	<i>Hyundai</i>	<i>Mini</i>	<i>Smart</i>
<i>Chevrolet</i>	<i>Jaguar</i>	<i>Mitsubishi</i>	<i>SSangYong</i>
<i>Chrysler</i>	<i>Jeep</i>	<i>Nissan</i>	<i>Subaru</i>
<i>Citroën</i>	<i>Kia</i>	<i>Opel/Vauxhall</i>	<i>Suzuki</i>
<i>Dacia</i>	<i>Lada</i>	<i>Peugeot</i>	<i>Toyota</i>
<i>Daihatsu</i>	<i>Lancia</i>	<i>Porsche</i>	<i>Volkswagen</i>
<i>Dodge</i>	<i>Land Rover</i>	<i>Renault</i>	<i>Volvo</i>
<i>Fiat</i>	<i>Lexus</i>	<i>Saab</i>	

Table 1. Studied automotive brands

Among this initial set of cars, we selected the top five selling models for each brand by reviewing the new passenger car registrations from 2007 to 2009. Pictures of the selected models were acquired from public sources on the Internet (e.g. Wiki Commons) and changed to grayscale with the background digitally removed to standardize the comparisons. All pictures showed the models slightly rotated, from the same (high front/left-side angle) perspective. The final outcome of this procedure was an initial set of 173 pictures of car models available in the German market in 2009. Some brands (e.g. Jaguar and Smart) had less than five different models available on the German market in 2009 and were, accordingly, represented by all their different models.

A model's styling strategy was estimated as the degree in which it looked similar to, or different from other models over Monö's (1997) three dimensions: a) other models within the present portfolio of the brand, b) the previous generation of the models, and c) competing models from different brands. Thus, in assessing the styling strategy used for each model, the students were asked to make visual comparisons for each model on each of the three dimensions.

The basis of comparison differed depending on the dimension. With respect to the present product portfolio dimension, each student evaluated how much one model per brand looked like the other models in the portfolio of the same brand ('How much does the car on the left look like the cars on the right?', 1: 'it looks very different' to 7: 'it looks very similar').

With respect to the succession of product generation dimension, we checked the German version of Wikipedia and found that 126 of the 173 models had a predecessor. For these models, we prepared additional pictures, and asked students to evaluate how much a model of a brand (shown on the left of the page) looked like its predecessor (on the right of the page) ('How much does the car on the left look like the car on the right?', 1: 'it looks very different' to 7: 'it looks very similar').

Finally, with respect to competing product dimensions, we established the main competitors for each model by going over car reviews in the three influential German car magazines: *Auto Motor und*

Sport, *Auto Bild* and *Auto Woche*. In specific, we selected those models of other brands that were most frequently mentioned in direct comparison tests between models (in German "Vergleichstests"). We limited our study to a maximum of four competitors for each model. Following this procedure, we established competitors for 156 out of the 173 models, again preparing additional pictures. For these models, students evaluated how much each model looked like its main competitors from other brands ('How much does the car on the left look like the cars on the right?', 1: 'it looks very different' to 7: 'it looks very similar'). Each student received an A4 booklet in which they had to rate one model of each brand on each dimension. Five separate booklets were created, each incorporating one model per brand, and thus a maximum of 39 comparisons per booklet. With 15 students participating in the task, each booklet was evaluated by three students. Before evaluating the cars, students were first trained by having them perform the same task on a smaller set of other products. Between performing the comparisons on each dimension, small breaks were scheduled for the students to reduce the fatigue and tediousness of the task.

The styling strategy for each model was calculated as the mean score of the 15 students (three per model) on each dimension. Prior to averaging the scores on each dimension over the booklets, we calculated the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) for each booklet to assess the inter-rater reliability between the students. On each dimension, the inter-rater reliability averaged over the booklets was assessed, and ranged from moderate for the competing products dimension (ICC=0.63), to almost perfect for the present product portfolio dimension (ICC=0.81), and the succession of product generations dimension (ICC=0.89). We therefore could average the students' evaluations on each dimension for each model as an estimate of the styling strategy employed by a brand for that model (following Dunn, 1989).

Brand strategy assessment

In a separate questionnaire survey, we asked 12 industry experts to assess the brands' strategy in four areas: (1) pricing, (2) quality (reliability), (3)

technological innovativeness and (4) market innovativeness. We also asked them to give an assessment of the brands' (1) overall performance and (2) brand strength. The assessments were made with respect to six statements. For each statement, the experts indicated the degree they found it representative for each brand (1: 'Strongly disagree' to 5: 'Strongly agree').

All industry experts had many years of experience from the automotive industry from working in areas such as R&D, marketing, sales and design and/or from educational institutes teaching automotive design. We used a 'snowball' (chain referral) technique in sampling the experts where four independently approached experts recommended other experts for our study. As a result, we not only reached experts known to us, but also people recognized for their industry expertise among their peers.

The brand strategy and performance for each brand were calculated as the mean score of the 12 experts with respect to each statement. Prior to averaging the brand strategy and performance scores, we calculated ICC for each assessment to assess inter-rater reliability. The inter-rater reliability for all the assessments were almost perfect (Dunn, 1989), ranging from 0.91 to 0.96. We could therefore reliably average the scores of the experts with respect to each assessment as an estimate of the brands' business strategies. Next, using the same brand score for all the models falling under a brand, we divided the different models in three categories to classify the degree they were representative of the different statements. In doing so, we sought to maintain equal size of the groups (without splitting up models with the same score into different groups, resulting in that some cases group sizes were slightly different).

RESULTS

The styling strategy scores were subjected to cluster analysis in order to reduce the styling strategies used over the 179 models to a small number of styling strategy types (groups) of related styling decisions. Following the procedure outlined by Calantone & Di Benedetto (2007), we used the SPSS based K-means clustering procedure to group the models' styling strategies scores over Monö's three dimensions. Prior

to performing the clustering analysis, we standardized the styling strategy scores to make them comparable. Cluster analysis does not hold a test for accepting one solution over another. We therefore explored multiple cluster solutions before settling on a final solution that was (1) mutually exclusive over the styling strategy scores and (2) revealed relevant differences in terms of brand strategy and performance.

As shown in Table 2, four distinct clusters emerged from the K-means clustering procedure incorporating all the 173 models (cases). The four clusters (typologies) contained 54, 34, 59 and 26 cases respectively. Together, they represent four main types of styling strategies, which are visible in the German passenger car market. In investigating the relevance of the different strategies, we compared the brand strategies underlying each model, and how these were distributed over the four clusters. We also studied the performance distribution over the four clusters. The results suggest that some styling strategy clusters are more commonly used for certain brand strategies and more linked to success and failure than other strategies. We summarize these conclusions below.

CLUSTER 1: 'MASS-APPEAL'

The second largest cluster contained car models that looked similar to the other models on all of Monö's three dimensions. The overall performance was highest for this cluster, suggesting that it is not only a common but also potentially profitable strategy to follow. The cluster also scored consistently high in terms of (premium-)pricing, quality, market innovativeness and technology innovativeness. Given the high similarity with competing model, the overall styling strategy seems to represent a 'mass-appeal' strategy by which companies seems to leverage their design to a broad set of consumers by following-up on the current trends in the market.

CLUSTER 2: 'EXPERIMENTATION'

This cluster contained car models that looked different to the other models on all of Monö's three dimensions. The overall performance and brand strength was among the lowest across the four clusters, suggesting that total differentiation (experimentation) potentially is a risky strategy. The

cluster also consistently held a bottom position in terms of (premium-)pricing, quality, technology innovativeness and market innovativeness. This said, eight models originated from successful brands, suggesting that it fulfills a role for such companies in potentially exploring new market opportunities.

CLUSTER 3: 'FOLLOWER'

Similar to the 'Experimentation' cluster, the largest cluster displayed low similarity with the present product portfolio and the succession of product generations. However, different from 'Experimentation' cluster, this (the largest) cluster displayed similarity with the competition. This result suggests that the lack of similarity over the first two dimensions may stem from attempts to follow-up on

trends in the market. While the brand strength did not seem to benefit substantially from seeking similarity with the competition, the overall performance was high for the models in this cluster. The cluster also displayed stronger scores in term of (premium-)pricing, quality, technology innovativeness and market innovativeness. As a result, the cluster seems to represents a common (successful) set of styling strategies.

CLUSTER 4: 'NURTURING'

In the smallest cluster, the models looked similar to other models of the same brand but different from competing models. In many ways, this cluster scored similar to the 'Mass-appeal' cluster in terms of pricing, quality, technology innovativeness and

	Overall N=173	Cluster 1 'Mass-appeal' N=54	Cluster 2 'Experimentation' N=34	Cluster 3 'Follower' N=59	Cluster 4 'Nurturing' N=26
Styling strategy					
Present product portfolio	0.00	0.56	-0.64	-0.60	1.09
Succession of product generations	0.00	0.73	-1.06	-0.49	0.79
Competing products	0.00	0.82	-1.31	0.34	-0.95
Brand strategy^a					
<i>Pricing</i>					
High	33% (58)	57% (31)	15% (5)	10% (6)	62% (16)
Medium	32% (55)	35% (19)	21% (7)	37% (22)	27% (7)
Low	35% (60)	7% (4)	65% (22)	53% (31)	11% (3)
<i>Quality (Reliability)</i>					
High	33% (57)	50% (27)	12% (4)	22% (13)	50% (13)
Medium	33% (58)	28% (15)	32% (11)	39% (23)	35% (9)
Low	33% (58)	22% (12)	56% (19)	39% (23)	15% (4)
<i>Technological innovativeness</i>					
High	32% (55)	50% (27)	15% (5)	20% (12)	42% (11)
Medium	35% (61)	33% (18)	35% (12)	37% (22)	35% (9)
Low	33% (57)	17% (9)	50% (17)	42% (25)	23% (6)
<i>Market innovativeness</i>					
High	33% (58)	46% (25)	18% (6)	24% (14)	50% (13)
Medium	32% (56)	33% (18)	29% (10)	37% (22)	23% (6)
Low	34% (59)	20% (11)	53% (18)	39% (23)	27% (7)
Performance^a					
<i>Overall performance</i>					
High	35% (60)	41% (22)	24% (8)	29% (17)	23% (8)
Medium	33% (58)	39% (21)	26% (9)	35% (21)	27% (9)
Low	32% (55)	20% (11)	50% (17)	35% (21)	50% (17)
<i>Brand strength</i>					
High	32% (55)	50% (27)	15% (5)	12% (7)	62% (16)
Medium	36% (63)	35% (19)	35% (12)	48% (28)	15% (4)
Low	32% (55)	15% (8)	50% (17)	41% (24)	23% (6)

Table 2. Cluster overview (^aSeparate one-way ANOVA tests on the average scores on each measure for brand strategy and performance revealed that for each measure differences between clusters were significant at $p < .01$)

market innovativeness. However, given the lower overall performance, the deviation from the competition emerged as a risky strategy, although it clearly built strong brand recognition.

DISCUSSION

Based on a cluster analysis of 173 car models, we distinguished four mutually exclusive clusters of styling decisions. We also investigated how the models in the different clusters relate to branding strategies in the passenger car market. The results suggest that automotive brands use a range of different styling strategies and that these strategies link with their overall business strategy. Overall, the resulting clusters provide a typology of commonly used strategies for styling of relevance for both theory and practice. For theory, we answered calls for more research on the management of styling activities (Creusen, 2011) as well as on the relation between design and strategy (Hertenstein & Platt, 1997). For practice, we provided a typology to support designers and managers in taking decision on brand styles. This said, how companies in different industries implement and profit from design activities such as styling is not necessarily the same. Gemser and Leenders (2001) found that companies profit differently from design depending on how mature the use of industrial design is within an industry. Thus, in extending the reported findings, future studies should explore the use of styling in different contexts to further clarify the specific objectives and constraints that frame styling activities within different industries and companies.

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